

Environmental Education Management as Instrument for Effective Waste Management for Cross River State's Sustainable Development

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Abstract

This study examines Environmental Education Management as an instrument for Effective Waste Management in Cross River State sustainable development. Two research questions and two null hypotheses was formulated to guide the study. A proportionate sampling technique was used to select to sample size of 210 school administrators 1,208 teachers for the study. The reliability Coefficient of 0.85 was established using Cronbach Alpha. The instrument title "Environmental Education Management for Effective Waste Management Questionnaire (EEMEQM)" was used for data collection. Mean rating score was used in answering the research questions while z – test statistics were used to test the null hypothesis. The finding revealed among others that indicates that all the strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State are relevant. It was recommended that environmental education policy should be put in place by various governments to enhance environmental safety.

Keywords: Environment, education, management, sustainable, development.

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Introduction

Globally there is a great need for environmental education to management environment effective due to the speedy changes of climatic and environment changes experiencing now a days. Environment management is a core service of environmental educationist. According to Uchegbu (1998) environmental management is the process of putting together those items of environmental nature where man exist so that man's penetration and exploitation do not have adverse effect on the environment. The author further maintained that environmental management is multidimensional and comprise a lot of things including checking and controlling factors and distribution of infrastructures in any way that will not hamper the nature physical environment. In a related view environmental Education is function of perception. In the same way environmental education has been perceived and defined in several ways since it entered the frontiers of the education enterprise. The environmental education Act defines environment education as the educational process dealing with man's relationship with his

natural and man –made surrounding and including the relation of population pollution, resources.

Sada (1988) in Cecilia (2013) sees environment as the sum total of all external condition influencing the growth and development of an organism. It was further explained that the environment is considered abused when injuries or complying element is introduced there by fouling it, reduces the satisfaction and utility derivable from it. The element that insults the environment are many and varied but most commonly manifest as waste therefore has the tendency of insulting the environment, by not well managed. As a result of changes in the nature of our food and consumption patterns, people’s attitude towards environment has changed drastically (Cecilia, 2013), people eat and litter the environment with cans of food drinks cellophane water proof and all sorts of water proof bags used for one kind of snacks or the other. This paper will not be complete with throwing little light sustainable development. Earth Summit Rio de Janeiro (1992) as Egbe (2012) defines sustainable development as development which will maintain an equilibrium management of natural resources without jeopardizing the life of the future generations. According to Dalal – Clayton (2002), sustainable development is commonly defined as “economic and social development that meets the needs of the generation without under mining the ability of future generation to meet their own needs”

Enu (2007) sustainable development is thus a contested territory with its ownership disputed by forces with very different interests. It is therefore difficult to foresee any slackening of the efforts of those who will continue to attempt to impose development to suit their ends, invoking “modernity; national integration, economic growth. Development is a process of change from a less desirable to a more desirable kind of society which is assist in terms of nation’s relative prosperity. In other words, development is a modernization of a country with emphasis on education, technology and industrialization as agents of transformation (Little and Leach in Offem, Aniah and Agunwa, 2018). Similarly Eze; Collin in Offem et al. (2018) sustainable development means building the community so that people can live comfortably without consuming all their resources also sustainable development as a development that calls for improving the quality of life for the people without increasing the use of their natural resources beyond the earth’s carrying capacity. Furthermore, sustain development is or means of achieving economic growth that is widely share and protects the earth’s vital resources allocation and depletion, conservation, transportation technology and urban and rural planning to the total human environment. Therefore, environmental education can be seen as a community activation process of engendering sustainable development through attitudinal change and practical activities connect with man’s use of the rich resources of nature. Its ultimate purpose is to improve the quality of the environment and sustain its resources for all people of all the everywhere (Ewa, 1995). Environmental education means a philosophical orientation entailing the conception of planning for a livable environment. It should be seen as both a positive way of promoting the beauty of the total environment and the negative measure of preventing nuisance in our environment (Cecilia, 2013), the essential approach is to educate man about his responsibilities is producing for his welfare as well as in ensuring that the environmental equilibrium is not disturbed to the extent of threatening the very existence of man.

Walton (1982) opined that environmental education is any type of education through brings about improved natural resource management and reduces environmental damages. Environmental education, is the education of member of that society about their immediate surrounding its climate and other natural phenomenon. In Cross River State, environmental management including planning for good and access roads, proper refuse disposing dump, cutting of grasses around the State planting of some shrub's ornamental trees and flowers etc.

Waste management, waste according Uchegbu (1998) means any unavoidable material resulting from human activities for which there is no immediate demand and must be disposed of. Uchegbu further refer to waste as materials which though may no longer be needed here, may become a feedstock or raw materials else here. Waste can be solid, semi – solid or liquid. Refuse can be disposed of, either as it is or after sustainable processing by using thermal or physical means of procession method. It can be processed in order to reduce the volume or for the other usages. In refuse, composting is one of the techniques of managing waste for effective sustainable development in our environment. According to Uchegbu (2002), In Nigeria, methods adopted for effective handling of solid waste include incineration, composting, land filling, shredding resource recovery, hos feeding and Bio – remediation. Waste as the name implies, does not mean total useless or worthless substances. It may be converted to raw materials or feedstock somewhere (Uchegbu, 2002). Piles of refuse in dump site can be picked and recycled and used as some other thing. Man in his physical activities produces waste of deference kinds in our local community open dumping system and burning of waste have been the most adopted method of waste disposal. Compositing has been seen as the biodegradation of the organic constituent of solid waste through aerobic microbial activity resulting in a sustainable, humus – like solid amendment called compost which can be used to stabilize soil from erosion, provide nutrients land replenish depleted organic matters lost through intensive farming (Cecilia, 2013). It is the conversion of refuse to table humus like substance not every waste is compostable. Non –bio gradable waste like white paper, plastic, waterproofs of any kind etc., are not compostable while organic matter like leaves, grass – cutting branches, agricultural waste etc. are compostable and can be transferred as compost. Waste has the tendency of insulting the environment, but not well managed. As a result of changes in the nature of our food and consumption in patterns, people's attitude towards environment has change drastically. People eat and liter the environment with can of food drinks, cellophane water proof and all sorts of water proof bags used for one kind of snacks or the other.

According to Uchegbu (1998) Waste mean unavoidable material resulting from human. Sada in Cecilia (2013) sees environment as the sum total of all external condition influencing the growth and development of an organism. More so, environment is considered abused when injuries or complying element is introduce thereby fouling it, reduces the satisfaction and utility derivable from it. The elements that insult the environment are many and varied but most commonly manifest as waste. Onyenze (2004) concluded that littering of our environment by various types of plastic container and polythene bags and sachets from water vendors, bread and snacks vendors, ice cream sellers et cafe some of the effects of environmental problems in our cities, Onyenze further concluded that poor environmental sanitation leads to easy spread of diseases (epidemic) and death, nuisance and aesthetic insult, management economic system

disruption etc. Open dumping of refuse improperly designed landfills, can pollute land, air waste and pose fire hazards and create unsightly nuisances, breed germs. Insect and diseases carrying rodents.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study was to investigate Environmental Education Management as an instrument for effective Waste Management in Cross River State for Sustainable Development. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Identified strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State?
2. Identified the challenges that result to lack of effective management of environmental education in Cross River State.

Research questions

The following research question was formulated as a guide to the study;

1. What are the identified strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State?
2. What are the challenges that result to lack of effective management of environmental education in Cross River State?

Statement of hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were posed to guide the study;

1. There is no significant difference between the mean rating of school administrators and teachers on the identified strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean rating of school administrators and teachers on the challenges that result to lack of effective management of environmental education in Cross River State.

Method

The researchers adopted a survey research design. The population of this study is made up of 330 school administrators and 6,600 teachers across the education zones of the state. The researchers adopted a proportionate sampling technique to select a sample size of 208 school administrators and 1,206 teachers. The researchers used structured 28 item questionnaire tack "Environmental Education Management for Effective Waste Management (EEMEWM) questionnaire. The questionnaire was structured on 4-point liker type rating scale of strongly agree (SA) = 4 points, Agree (A) = 3 points, Disagree (D) = 2 points and Strongly Disagree (SA) = 1 point. The instrument was duly validated by three experts in the department of Educational Administration and Planning, measurement and evaluation and Environmental

education, of University of Calabar. The instrument reliability co-efficient was established by using Cronbach Alpha that yielded 0.85 which was considered high for the study. The researchers and three research assistants administered 1,500 questionnaires to the respondents which was duly filled and return on the spot. The researchers used mean rating to analyze the two research questions while z-test analysis was used to test the two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was that a mean response of 2.50 and above were considered active while below 2.50 were inactive.

Results

Research question 1

What are the identified strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State? Data in table 1 revealed that all the items for both school administrators and teachers had high mean scores ranging from 2.52 to 3.95 respectively. These high mean scores indicate that all the strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State are relevant.

Table 1: Mean scores of school administrators and teachers on the identified strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State.

S/N	Items	School Admins. (\bar{x})	Teachers (\bar{x})	Remark
1.	Implementing effective environmental policy	2.71	2.95	Active
2.	Initiating effective environmental education programme	3.01	2.91	Active
3.	State government introducing a special working committee waste disposal	2.82	2.65	Active
4.	Environmental education curriculum needs to be expanded to ensure proper vital value	3.05	2.72	Active
5.	Incineration should be encouraged in the state	2.60	2.71	Active
6.	Government provision of many barn disposal containers in the state	3.04	3.64	Active
7.	Land filling should be encouraged	3.00	2.95	Active
8.	Waste compositing should be encouraged	3.01	3.21	Active
9.	Waste dumping should be reduced	2.68	3.01	Active
10.	Recycling should be encouraged	2.57	2.59	Active
11.	Provision of taskforce to ensure adherence	3.21	3.02	Active
12.	Bioremediation should be encouraged	2.82	3.95	Active
13.	Tree planting should encourage	2.56	2.61	Active
14.	Compulsory monthly sanitation should be encouraged	2.60	2.60	Active
15.	Community cooperative should be encouraged	2.58	2.52	Active
	Grand mean (\bar{x})	2.84	2.74	

Research question 2

What are the challenges that result to lack of effective management of environmental education in Cross River State? Table 2 indicates that all the items for both school administrators and teachers had high mean scores ranging from 2.52 to 3.26 exception or item 4 shows that all are challenges created by lack of effective management of environmental education in Cross River State. Item 4 had men scores of 2.31 and 2.43 for both school administrators and teachers respectively. This further revealed that both school administrators and teachers in Cross River State did not accept that “lack of accessible road in the town” is among the challenges that result to lack of effective management of environmental education in the state.

Table 2: Mean Score of school administrators and teachers on challenges that result to lack of effective management of environmental education in Cross River State.

S/N	Items	School Administrators (\bar{x})	Teachers (\bar{x})	Remark
1.	Changes in policies	3.25	3.00	Active
2.	School has no well mapped out towns	2.98	2.70	Active
3.	Inadequate management facilities	3.00	3.26	Active
4.	Regular training for personnel	2.31	2.43	Inactive
5.	Lack of motivation	2.91	3.02	Active
6.	Poor attitude of community members	3.21	3.08	Active
7.	Environmental sustainability culture	2.70	2.61	Active
8.	Inadequate funding	2.64	2.76	Active
9.	Location of school	3.01	2.85	Active
	Grand mean (\bar{x})	2.89	2.85	

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean rating of school administrators and teachers on the identified strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State. Table 3 shown that the z – calculated of 1.40 is less than z – critical of 1.97 at 1508 degree of freedom and 0.08 level of significances. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there is no significance different between the mean rating of school administrators and teachers on the identified strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State.

Table 3: Z-test analysis of the differences between the mean rating of school administrative and teachers on identified strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State.

Respondent	M	(\bar{x})	Sd	df	Z cal	Zcrit	prob	remark
School administrators	208	2.56	07.6	1508	1.40	1.97	0.05	N/S
Teachers	1,206	2.76	0.85					
P < 0.05								

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean rating of school administrators and teachers on the challenges that result to lack of effective management of environmental education in Cross River State. Table 4 indicates that the z – calculated of 1.45 is less than z – critical of 1.97 at 1509 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. There null hypothesis is accepted meaning that there is no significant difference between the school administrators and teachers on the challenges that result to lack of effective management of environmental education is Cross River State.

Table 4: z-test analysis of the difference between the mean rating of school administrators and teachers on challenges that result to lack of effective management of environmental education in Cross River State.

Respondent	N	(\bar{x})	SD	df	z-cal	z-crit	prob	Remark
School administrators	208	2.89	07.7	1509	1.45	1.97	005	No significance
Teachers	1,206	2.78	0.84					

P < 0.05

Discussion of findings

All the fifteen (15) items of both school administrators and teachers' opinion in table 1 obtained a high mean rating of 2.52 to 3.95. Also, the high grand mean of 2.84 and 2.74 respectively and in table 3. Z – Cal is less than the z – critical of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that the opinion of both school administrators and teachers are in accord that all the items as the identified strategies adopted for effective management of environment in Cross River State. These findings are in line with Uchegbu (1998) who concluded that incineration, composition, land filling, shredding, hog teaching, Resource recovery, Bioremediation etc. are some possible strategies for effective management of environment in our society. Uchegbu further added that minimizing waste and maximizing re-use and recycling is another treasure that should be valued as far as strategies for effective management of our environment is concerned. To Obasi (2003) the above findings support that development of educational programme in the school curriculum, that addresses issues on proper, environmental management, and that it should be in such a way as to motivate teachers and students on the need as to motivate teachers and students on the need to participate and appreciate the value of good environment. The above findings support that development of education as programme in the school curriculum that addresses issues on proper environmental management, and that it should be in such a way as to motivate teachers and students on the need to participate and appreciate the value of good environment Government strong policy with adequate legislation on environmental friendliness

will lead to a con-ordinated and comprehensive planning and care of our environment (Onyenze, 2004).

In table 2 nine (9) items for both school administrators and teachers had a high mean score of 2.52 to 3.26. And the grand mean of 2.89 and 2.85 respectively are high. The z – calculated of 1.45 is less that the z – critical of 1.97 at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that both school administrators and teachers’ opinion are support of the items on the challenges that result to lack of effective management of environmental education in Cross River State. These study findings are in agreement with the view of Onyenze (2004) who was of the opinion that poor environmental sanitation, ease the spread of disease and deaths, nuisance and aesthetic insult. Onyenze also added that open dumping of refuse of indiscriminately can pollute the land, air and water pose fire hazard, create unsightly nuisance and disease carry rodents. In supporting the above statement Uchegbu (2002) stated that poor and unkept environment are always abuse of the natural environment and at the same time create an eye sore psychological problem and lacks concentration on the inhabitants.

Conclusion

With respect to environmental education management, the public have greater advantage because most of their attitude will be change to conform the environmental sustainability for sustainable development goal. Critically-minded individual are developed with the help of environmental education based on their environmental protection knowledge.

Recommendations

Base on the finding of this study, the following recommendations were made

1. Environmental management policy should be put in place by various governments to enhance environmental safety.
2. Government should introduce environmental programme at all level of education to create basic awareness about environmental protection.
3. Government should re-enforce monthly environmental clean – up exercise.

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